

Basalt amendment as a key driver for carbon sequestration

Rising atmospheric CO₂ and climate change require carbon sequestration alongside emission reductions. Soil sequestration is enhanced by basalt amendment, which accelerates mineral weathering, stabilizes carbon in soils, and reduces water usage. Enhanced rock weathering is commonly known in the field of carbon storage, being considered a source of nutrients and a tool for C-sequestration. At the Sekem Wahat farm, researchers tested various basalt and compost amendments across 12 plots. The mixtures included basalt concentrations of 27wt% and 5wt% relative to compost, applied at a rate of 48 tons of compost per hectare and season. Results showed that wheat productivity increased by more than 15% following basalt application compared to conventional management. Soil analyses conducted over two years showed a substantial rise in nutrient availability, with potassium reaching 500 mg kg⁻¹ and phosphorus reaching 70 mg kg⁻¹, indicating significant soil fertility enrichment. In terms of climate benefits, preliminary assessments suggest a carbon dioxide removal potential ranging from -1.4 to -10 Mg CO₂e per hectare per year at a basalt application rate of 35 Mg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. Additionally, operational performance improved, with a 15% reduction in production costs and a 15% increase in soil organic matter content.

Figure 3 Data reveals significant improvements in plant development metrics for both wheat and alfalfa, including enhanced grain weight, plant height, and root growth, directly attributable to basalt/compost applications.

KEYWORDS

Soil Organic Carbon; Compost; Basalt

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